

Avatar-Enabled Virtual Therapist Application for Cognitive Rehabilitation Intervention in Traumatic Brain Injury and Post-Stroke Patients

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ABSTRACT

The quality of life of post-stroke and traumatic brain injury (TBI) patients usually drops after the end of rehabilitation due to their discharge from the hospital. This study explores the impact of adding the avatar of a “virtual therapist” to a 3D application used in hospitals for cognitive rehabilitation, allowing patients to continue using this application without the presence of a real therapist after rehabilitation discharge. A sample of 5 patients from Alcoitão Rehabilitation Medicine Centre were asked to continue their cognitive rehabilitation with the new avatar-enabled application for minimum 6 sessions. Comparing pre and post intervention, significant improvements in MoCA and WMS cognitive measurements were found suggesting effectiveness of using an avatar as the virtual therapist for cognitive rehabilitation in later stages of TBI and post stroke rehabilitation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Stroke and traumatic brain injury represent two major causes of death and disability, often leaving lasting cognitive deficits (Wafa et al., 2020). The survivors may experience a range of cognitive impairments. Dysfunction in memory, orientation, language, attention, and executive skills are the most frequently observed (Tatemichi et al., 1994). Patients with cognitive impairment often need to go through cognitive rehabilitation in a clinical facility, however, when they are sent home, the rehabilitation process abruptly stops. In addition, the improvements in executive functions require a more intense treatment approach (Oliveira et al., 2022). Longitudinal studies found that the quality-of-life scores reported upon rehabilitation discharge usually do not last (Schindel et al., 2021). The capacity to use Virtual Reality (VR) to carry out rehabilitation outside of the hospital environment and into patients' homes (Chen et al., 2019) creates opportunities for further assistance, removing constraints related to distance and encouraging long-term rehabilitation.

This study proposes an addition of a “virtual therapist” to an existing 3D serious game digital application named Systemic Lisbon Battery (SLB), to overcome this challenge. SLB is a validated application used for cognitive rehabilitation on several hospitals. Various studies have found evidence that SLB is a useful tool for improving cognitive functioning on different populations (Gamito et al., 2020; Oliveira et al., 2022). The added “virtual therapist” will help the patient perform simple daily routine tasks in VR. This way, the patients can continue their rehabilitation process for a longer time after being discharged from the hospital. The objective of this study is to find out if the use of this “virtual therapist” leads to cognitive improvements in post-stroke and traumatic brain injury patients.

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants

10 patients (5 post-stroke and 5 traumatic brain injury) including 8 males and 2 females, aged from 29 to 70, from Alcoitão Medicine and Rehabilitation Centre (Lisbon, Portugal), suffering from cognitive impairment. 5 patients were assigned to the control group and 5 to the experimental group.

2.2. Measures

Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA); Frontal Assessment Battery (FAB); Wechsler Memory Scale (WMS); Motivation for Rehabilitation Scale (MORE); World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF). All the measures were validated for the Portuguese population. Each patient was evaluated in two different moments – before and after the intervention.

2.3. Procedure

Each participant had 6 to 10 training sessions over different periods ranging from 1 to 4 months. Patients were assigned to two groups: a control group, which used the SLB application with the assistance from a "real" therapist; and an experimental group, which used the avatar-enabled version of SLB as "virtual therapist" developed for this study (Figure 1). The sessions from both groups were conducted in the hospital setting and the therapist remained present during these sessions to ensure that everything went smoothly and only intervened if necessary. To get the patients more familiar with using the application, they had their first SLB session with the help of a real therapist before moving forward to the avatar version. The application included different levels of difficulty, and for analysis purposes, it actively collects data on the patient's progress and offers various instructions and tasks to the participants. This feature facilitates monitoring the patients remotely by a real therapist for modifying and optimizing the process. MoCA, FAB, and WMS, were applied pre- and post-intervention on both groups. The other two scales of MORE and WHOQOL-BREF were only applied on experimental group. Repeated Measures ANOVAs was performed to measure the differences between two moments in time.

Figure 1 Avatar-enabled SLB Application

3. RESULTS

Regarding experimental group, statistically significant improvements were found in MoCA and WMS tests. MoCA showed an improvement ($F(1,4) = 22.86; p = 0.009$) in the mean results of the participants from the first assessment ($M = 22.8; SD = 2.68$) to the second assessment ($M = 26.8; SD = 1.30$). WMS also showed positive results ($F(1,4) = 19.66; p = 0.011$) on the memory quotient from the first assessment ($M = 86.4; SD = 9.74$) to the second assessment ($M = 106.2; SD = 5.97$). FAB showed a improvement on the mean scores from the first assessment ($M = 16.2; SD = 0.84$) to the second assessment ($M = 17.6; SD = 0.55$), although it was not statistically significant ($F(1,4) = 7.54; p = 0.052$). Neither the MORE (first assessment: $M = 113.6; SD = 7.27$; second assessment: $M = 110.6; SD = 11.50$) nor the WHOQOL-BREF (first assessment: $M = 79.4; SD = 8.65$; second assessment: $M = 80.1; SD = 9.81$) scales showed statistically significant changes between the assessments ($p > 0.05$). However, the mean scores of the participants were high on both scales compared to normative data. Regarding control group, although MoCA, FAB, and WMS did not show any statistically significant results ($p > 0.05$), the data showed slight positive trends across all scales.

4. CONCLUSIONS

There are recent studies showing the positive impact of an avatar in cognitive rehabilitation for older people (Lee et al., 2024), and in the improvement in Quality of Life of individuals with a diagnosis of schizophrenia (Şahinbaş, Tekin & Gökbay, 2024). However, there is a lack of information regarding acquired brain injuries (ABI) patients, which motivated this study. The improvement in MoCA scores from the baseline to the post intervention assessment is substantial and suggests that the avatar-enabled SLB intervention has a meaningful impact on cognitive function. Similarly, the WMS scores showed a notable increase between assessment points, indicating improved memory performance. Although the Frontal Assessment Battery (FAB) did not reach statistical significance, the trend toward improvement is noteworthy, suggesting that with a larger sample size, the intervention might demonstrate significant effects on frontal lobe functions. Although MORE and WHOQOL-BREF measurements did not show statistically significant changes, the high mean scores on both scales suggest

that participants were highly motivated and had a positive outlook both before and after the intervention. The sustained motivation and optimism are critical factors that can enhance the overall effectiveness of cognitive rehabilitation (Yoshida et al., 2022).

While the cognitive scores of the control group were not statistically significant, the slight positive trend across all scales anticipates a potential benefit of SLB sessions. These trends, observed in MoCA, FAB, and WMS scores, could be of practical significance and warrant further investigation with a larger sample size (Oliveira et al., 2022). Moreover, qualitative feedback from participants indicated perceived improvements in cognitive function, suggesting that the intervention may have subjective benefits not fully captured by the quantitative measures used.

The current study was limited by a small sample size and the preliminary nature of data collection for the control group since the gap between each session was longer than the experimental group, and the cognitive tests were not immediately applied after the last session due to logistics difficulties and availability of the patients. Future research with a larger cohort, longer follow-up period, and more frequent sessions and particularly with less gap time between the sessions is needed to determine the potential cognitive benefits of SLB sessions more conclusively. Overall, the results suggest that the “virtual therapist” and its associated avatar could potentially be at least as impactful as a real therapist, if not more, in the later stages of the rehabilitation process, providing a beneficial tool for continuing therapy after hospital discharge.

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